

NIR Response of Gold Nanoparticles for Biological Detection

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Gold Nanoparticles (GNs) have been widely used during the past few years in various technical and biomedical applications. In particular, the resonance optical properties of nanometer sized particles have been employed to design biochips and biosensors used as analytical tools. The optical properties of non-functionalized GNs and core-gold nanoshells play a crucial role for the design of biosensors where gold surface is used as sensing component. Due to plasmonic coupling with electromagnetic fields, GNs exhibit excellent optical tunability at visible and near-infrared frequencies leading to sharp peaks in their spectral extinction.

In this paper, we study how the optical properties of gold nanoparticles and core-gold nanoshells are changed as a function of different sizes, shapes, composition and biomolecular coating with characteristic shifts towards near-infrared region, 750-900nm. We show that the optical tunability in this region can be carefully checked for particle sizes falling in the range 100-150nm. Such tunability in the range 750-900 nm is particularly important in biosystems, because the high transmittivity properties characterizing many biological tissues.

In addition, the optical response of GNs clusters will be discussed both using theoretical and numerical tools. Finally, by using a Scanning Near Field Microscopy, some preliminary experimental results on the NIR response of GNs, when absorbed by mouse cells, will be presented and discussed.

References

M. D'Acunto, D. Moroni, O. Salvetti, *Advances in Optical Technologies*, 2012